

Regarding Political Relations of Abusayid Mirzo with the Ruler of Aqquyuns

Dr. Khurshid T. Fayziev

PhD, Associate Professor the State Museum of Temurid History Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: This article informs about political activities of Sultan Abusayid, the ruler of Temurids Empire, his struggle for the throne of Samarqand, military, political and embassy relations on the issue of Western Iran and Azerbaijan regions with representatives of Aqquyuns dynasty Hasanbek and Qaraquyuns Jahanshah.

The role and importance of the territories of Western Iran and Azerbaijan[1] in the Temurid kingdom were both politically and economically important. The essence of the Sultanate's military-political relations with local principalities and various ethnic groups in these regions are not only to control Western Iran and Azerbaijan, but also to be seen from time to time as a place where conflicting political and economic interests of major powers should collide.

KEY WORDS: Temurids, Aqquyuns, Qaraquyuns, Amir Temur, Shahrukh Mirzo

INTRODUCTION

It is known that after the death of Shahrukh Mirzo, contradictions arose between the Temurid princes for the throne. In this situation, one of the urgent tasks is to study the personality of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, who, thanks to his long-term policy, managed to centralize the kingdom, was guided by state security and interests in internal and foreign policy. In this regard, this article describes the military, urinary and diplomatic ties of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo with Jahanshah Qaraquyunlu, Hasanbek Aqquyunlu in matters of Khorasan, Western Iran and Azerbaijan region. After all, the coverage of the activities of individuals who occupied a special place in this historical process in solving the general problems of the history of Uzbek statehood plays an important role in filling the deer missing in our history.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this research, "Matlai sadayn va majmai bakhrayn" by Abdurazzaq Samarqandiy, "Geneology of the Temurids" by Turgun Fayziev, "Habib us-siyar fi akhbori afrodi bashar" by Ghiyasiddin ibn Humamiddin Khandamir, "Habib us-siyar" by Ghiyasiddin ibn Humamiddin Khandamir, "The legacy of the Timurids" by S. F. Dale, Timurids in Transition : Turko-Persian politics and acculturation in medieval Iran by M. Subtelny are used as main sources.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is a qualitative research using the content analysis approach. More than ten scientific works are chosen to analyze regarding political relations of Abusayid Mirzo with the ruler of Aqquyuns. Besides that, the author had used journals and articles to collect data related to the research.

RESULTS

As it is known from history, despite the fact that large states of that time did not directly enter into military conflicts, they would continue to fight for the place of a political leader in the region of the Near and Middle East through various ethnic groups in Western Iran and Azerbaijan. In particular, the Akkuyunlu and Qaraquyunly dynasties acted as a "device" in their relations, which elucidated the relationship between the regions.

After the death of Amir Temur, during the short reign of Mironshah and his sons, the position of the Temurids in these areas decreased and the sphere of influence sharply diminished. This was exactly the situation for the Qaraquyuns. The battle between the Temurids and the Qaraquyuns in 1408 ended with the victory of Qara Yusuf. The Aqquyuns, an ally of the Temurids, had also lost their position in the political arena during this period.

In order to resolve the situation in his favor Shahrukh Mirzo organized several military campaigns in the territories of Azerbaijan and Western Iran and managed to subdue the Qaraquyuns. In turn, the Akkuyuns who were considered rivals to

Regarding Political Relations of Abusayid Mirzo with the Ruler of Aqquyuns

Qaraquyuns under the influence of Rum Sultans were supported by Shahrukh Mirzo. After all, the Aqquyuns, the political force, which had been supported by the sultanate since the time of Amir Temur, was supposed to serve as a "wall" against the Egyptian and Roman states. Shahrukh Mirzo also continued this policy in his relations with these countries and began to support Akkuyuns in the political arena in various ways. The Aqquyuns obeyed Shahrukh Mirzo and tried to improve relations. As it is noted by Abdurazzaq Samarkandiy, "From the time when Hazrat Sahibkiran's (Temur) victorious cavalry reached Azerbaijan, until the time when hazrat khaqan sayyid's royal sun shone on his property, Amir Qara Usman was always in the status of nobility and obedience"[2].

At the time of the transfer of the Sultanate to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, the sphere of influence of the Akkuyuns was expanding in the political life of Azerbaijan and the region of Western Iran.

Sultan Abusayid Mirzo was the son of Sultan Muhammad Mirzo and was born in 1424[3]. His political career dates back to 1450. In the years following Shahrukh Mirzo's death, during the struggle for the throne between his descendants, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo captured Turkestan (Yassa) and began to claim the throne of Samarqand.

The ruler of Samarqand, Abdullah Mirzo, launched a military operation against Abusayid Mirzo and drew troops against him. Abusayid Mirzo appealed to Abulhayr for military assistance. Abulhayr came to Turkestan, accompanied by the troops of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo to Tashkent, and from there to Khojand. The armies of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo and Abulhayr passed through Mirzachul and met Abdullah Mirzo's army in Bulunghur. In June 1451, a battle took place between the two armies near the village of Shiraz, which is in the south of the Bulunghur steppe. As a result, Abulhayrkhan defeated Abdullah Mirzo's large army. Abdullah Mirzo was killed during the battle. Sultan Abusayid Mirzo took the throne of Samarqand.

Abusayid Mirzo, who wanted to restore the power of the empire during the reign of Amir Temur, also launched military operations to annex the territory of Khorasan.

After the death of Abulqasim Babur Mirzo, who was in Mashhad in March 1457, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo took control of Herat. In imitation of Shahrukh Mirzo, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo gave the throne of Samarqand to his eldest son Sultan Ahmad Mirzo and declared Herat as a capital.

However, during this period, a specific political crisis was taking place in the political life of Khorasan. There were several independent humorists in the region, and the internal conflicts between them were strong. Jahanshah, a representative of the Qaraquyunlu dynasty, who took advantage of the Temurid conflict, captured the city of Herat. However, Jahanshah also failed to establish sufficient control over Khorasan, a region of Western Iran. According to historian Khandamir, Hasanbek, aqquyunlu, began to prevent the Jahanshah from ruling the region[4]. At the same time, the conflict between the Qaraquyuns was confusing the political situation in the region. In particular, the return of Khorasan to Temurid rule undermined Jahanshah's influence in the region's political arena. Indeed, Jahanshah's son, Pirbudak, the viceroy of the Persian provinces, revolted against him after his father's peace treaty with Sultan Abusayid Mirzo on the Khorasan issue[5]. Jahanshah succeeded in suppressing the rebellion and ordered the assassination of his son Pirbudak. This caused many emirs to turn away from the ruler.

Jahanshah, who had suppressed the revolt, now launched a military operation against another rival, Hasanbek of Aqqoyunlu. The phase of the eternal conflict between the Qaraquyunlu and Aqquyunlu dynasties during the reign of Hasanbek and Jahanshah ended with the defeat of the latter. This has led to an increase in the influence of Hasanbek as a leading force in the region of Western Iran and Azerbaijan. Therefore, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, who conquered Khorasan, had to enter into political relations with Hasanbek on the issue of the region of Western Iran.

Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, who united Maverannahr and Khorasan and increased his sultanate status, tried to include the territories of Azerbaijan and Western Iran in the sultanate after the Jahanshah incident.

Hasanbek sent his envoys to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, who was standing on the Kolpush pasture, and reminded that the people of Qaraquyunlu had never been loyal to Amir Temur and the Temurids, and that the people of Aqquyunlu were loyal to the family of Hazrat Sahibkiran.

On July 10, 1468, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo sent a letter[6] to Hasanbek, the leader of the Aqquyunlu. The letter mentioned that Amir Temur gave Diyarbakr province to Hasanbek's great father Qara Usman, that in the post-Amir Temur period Tabriz belonged to Mironshah Mirzo and to give back the land to Abusayid Mirzo, instead of this Sultan promised[7] him Egypt and Shom.

Meanwhile, the son of Jahanshah from Qaraquyunlu came to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo and conveyed the message[8]: "What I have under my control is the real property of the victorious king." Respecting the ambassadors of Hussein Ali, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo sent a following message: "Now the flag of the world is flying towards Azerbaijan, and after our visit, whatever happens in the interests of the state will happen"[9] and allowed them to go.

When the Temurid army arrived in Ray[10] province, Hussein Ali Qaraquyunlu launched a military action to fight against Hasanbek Aqquyunlu. However, the news that Sultan Abusayid Mirzo's army had reached Tabriz posed a threat to Hussein Ali's Qaraquyunlu army, and some of his emirs came to Hasanbek Aqquyunlu and some to Sultan Abu Sayyid Mirzo. Inspired by this, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo intensified his military campaign to Western Iran. During this period, Hasanbek sent his nephew Yusufbek as an ambassador to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo. According to historian Ghiyasiddin Khandamir, Hasanbek, through his nephew,

Regarding Political Relations of Abusayid Mirzo with the Ruler of Aqquyuns

conveyed the following message to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo: "For about a hundred years, our ancestors have adhered to the course of commitment and statehood for the family of Hazrat Shahibkiran Amir Temur. Today, without departing from this path, I have liberated the Persia[11] and Iraq[12] provinces from the clutches of the enemy and handed them over to the high-ranking officials. The hope is that you will allow us to stay in this reedbed until end of winter, when the snow on the roads is melted and we have the opportunity to return to Diyarbakr"[13].

It was clear from Hasanbek's address to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo that during this period the Aqquyuns were obliged to take a compromise with the Temurids. For, although Hasanbek had succeeded against Jahanshah in the territory of Western Iran, it was not in his interest to go against Sultan Abusayid Mirzo. However, on the other hand, Hasanbek first robbed Jahanshah of his horde when the opportunity arose, conveying the same words of "necessity and request"[14] as his appeal to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo.

This is probably why Sultan Abusayid continued his military action, ignoring the words of Mirzo Hasanbek.

Sultan Abusayid conveyed the following reply to Mirzo Hasanbek through the ambassadors Mirzo Mahmud and Khoja Loq: "Fortunate troop is on his way to that land. After we have come we will act reasonably "[15].

During the military march, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo didn't give a definite answer to the ambassadors of Hasanbek Aqquyunlu and Husain Ali Qaraqyunlu, and continued his martial campaign.

Sultan Abusayid Mirzo held a meeting with the emirs on the issue of choosing a suitable place from the cold to spend the winter. According to the council's decision, Hasanbek will be expelled from Qarabakh and they will spend the winter there. However, after Sultan Abusayid Mirzo's embassy response to Aqquyunlu the food problem in the military camp was raised, then it was decided to go to Mahmudabad[16]. The matter was that, Hasanbek blocked the roads directed to Khorasan, Iraq and Persia and didn't allow anyone to enter the camp. The only hope was in the food sent by Shirvanshas's ship, who was an ally of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo. Historian Khandamir pointed out that at that time the famine and starvation among the army reached such a level that the price of weighing grain rose to ten dinars of bran[17].

However, Shirvanshah who feared Hasanbek, extended allied relations with Sultan Abusayid Mirzo. The army, which was in a difficult situation was forced to move from Mahmudabad to Ardabil[18]. In the swampy areas of the road, many horses of army sink into the mud.

On January 26, 1469 Hasanbek gave a peaceful proposal to Abusayid Mirzo. In order to agree on the terms of the truce, some influential beks headed by Amir Sayyid Mazid were sent to designated place by Sultan Abusayid Mirzo. However, Amir Sayyid Mazid made unpardonable mistake there. So, when Amir saw that army of Khorasan who came with him outnumbered the army of Aqquyuns, began a sudden attack. Although, firstly the Temurid army was victorious, but then Hasanbek's ambushed troops attacked, in the result many Khorasan emirs and army were defeated. In order to rectify the situation after the incident, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo sent to Hasanbek's court Amir Ghiyasiddin Muhammad bin Amir Jaloliddin Abdvahob bin Amir Ghiyasiddin bin Amir Kamoliddin bin Amir Sayyid Qavomiddin, one of the governors of Mozandaran, to renew the truce. At that time, when Hasanbek welcomed the Sayyids with bow and respect, and decided to conclude a truce, Sayyid Ardabiliy who was sent to the court of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, returned and reported that "now people of Khorasan in an extremely bad situation and should not tolerate peace and reconciliation"[19]. It was a pretext to Hasanbek sent his horse patrol to Sultan Abusayid Mirzo's whereabouts. The Sultan was forced to flee. However, the sons of amir Hasanbek captured the Sultan and brought him to his father's residence. Although, Hasanbek received Sultan Abusayid Mirzo with a great respect, later, on the advice of a group of emirs, he handed him over to Yodgor Muhammad Mirzo who was a descendant of Shahrukh Mirzo. On February 5, 1469, the prince sentenced Sultan Abusayid Mirzo to death for the blood of his grandmother Gawharshad Begim.

The body of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo was brought to Heart and buried in the Temurid shrine near the Madrasah of Gawharshad Begim[20].

This was the end of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo's political relations with the Aqquyuns.

During this period of study, there are a number of interesting aspects of the political relations of the Temurids with the Aqquyuns. Saying exactly, why did Sultan Abusayid Mirzo try to strengthen political ties with the Qaraquyuns without entering into an alliance with the Aqquyuns on the issue of Western Iran?

Secondly, he continued military action against Hasanbek, who proposed an alliance.

In our opinion, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, who was a contender for Azerbaijan and Western Iran, regarded Qaraqyunli Jahanshah instead of Hasanbek, as a leading force in the regions of Azerbaijan and Western Iran and tried to reach a mutually beneficial agreement with him. According to historian Khandamir, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo, in his negotiations with amir Jahanshah on the Khorasan issue, informed that "an armistice would be strong only if Mirzo Shahrukh Guragan will be satisfied with the country of Azerbaijan and give back Persia and Iraq to their present proprietor, for Us and our Supreme Court." Later, as the situation demanded, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo decided to establish political relations with the Qaraqyunlus, and if Jahanshah will be agreed with the terms of the Sultan, there would be no objection to their rule in Azerbaijan. However, this position of Abusayid Mirzo contradicted the interests of the Aqquyuns, who have always been a contender for Azerbaijan. The defeat of Jahanshah strengthened Hasanbek's political position in the region.

Regarding Political Relations of Abusayid Mirzo with the Ruler of Aqquyuns

Hasanbek recognized that Abusayid Mirzo's goal was to include Western Iran and Azerbaijan to his kingdom, then conveyed to the emirs of Sultan coming to Tabriz, in particular to Amir Mazid, that the emirs of Chaghatay should leave Tabriz, and informed that this land he handed to his son Oghurlu Muhammad. However, when he heard that the Temurid army had arrived to Sultaniya, he moved from Tabriz and settled in Qarabagh[21]. After Hasanbek's action, the sons of Jahanshah from Qaraqyunlu came to Abusayid Mirzo. The Sultan received them with respect and attention.

CONCLUSION

When Amir Hasanbek was informed about an alliance of the Temurids with the Qaraqyuns, he also conveyed the above-mentioned "offence" to the residence of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo through his ambassadors. Of course, Hasanbek, like Jahanshah, did not want to give Western Iran and Azerbaijan to the Temurids and rule under their leadership. However, taking into consideration complexity of political and military situation in the region, Hasanbek had officially announced to submit the Sultan. When the Temurid army moved towards Tabriz indeed, he resisted handing over the land to "royal officials.". Probably for this reason, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo also did not believe to Hasanbek's words of alliance and tried to use the sons of Jahanshah Qaraqyunlu in the fight against him. In general, Sultan Abusayid Mirzo did not trust the representatives of both rival dynasties in this military campaign. He remained the same position in the political relations with them, that is, the matter of how the territories of the region would be distributed and who would govern them remained unclear. This was a major mistake of Sultan Abusayid Mirzo relations with the political forces of the region. In his time, Shahrukh Mirzo had relations with these dynasties in the case of both Western Iran and Azerbaijan, and their interests were taken into account without disturbing the political balance in the region. In this way, Shahrukh Mirzo managed to keep the Aqquyunlu and Qaraqyunlu in his sphere of influence.

Sultan Abusayid Mirzo was the last ruler among the Temurids who reunited the territories of the kingdom after Shahrukh Mirzo's period. During his 18-year reign he sought to establish order and justice in the country. However, his reckless military policy toward the Western Iran didn't bring him success.

REFERENCES

- 1) Samarqandiy, A. (2008). *Matlai sadayn va majmai baxrayn*. Volume II. Parts 1-2 (1429 - 1470) Translation from Persian, foreword and comments by A.Urinbaev. Annotated index of geographical names compiled by O. Buriev, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
- 2) Fayziev, T. (1995). *Geneology of the Temurids*. Tashkent, "Yozuvchi" Publishing House
- 3) Ghiyasiddin ibn Humamiddin Khandamir. (2013). *Habib us-siyar fi akhbori afrodi bashar*. Translation from Persian, authors of the introduction by Jalil Hazratkulov, Ismail Bekjanov. Authors of comments by Ashraf Ahmedov, Ismail Bekjanov, Tashkent. "Uzbekistan"
- 4) Dale, S. F. (1998). The legacy of the Timurids. *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 8(1), 43-58.
- 5) Subtelny, M. (2007). *Timurids in Transition: Turko-Persian politics and acculturation in medieval Iran* (Vol. 19). Brill.
- 6) Subtelny, M. E. (1988). Socioeconomic Bases of Cultural Patronage under the Later Timurids. *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 20(4), 479-505.
- 7) Manz, B. F. (2020). Iranian Elites under the Timurids. In *Trajectories of State Formation across Fifteenth-Century Islamic West-Asia* (pp. 257-282). Brill.
- 8) Doniyorov, A., Kariyev, A., Aminov, H., & Karimov, N. (2021). The Level of Study of the Religious Image of Mavarounnahr in the IX-XII Centuries. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(1), 413-423.
- 9) Omonov, Q., & Karimov, N. (2020). Importance Of Ancestral Heritage. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(09), 196-202.
- 10) Khudoyberdiyevich, D. A., & Rakhmonqulovich, K. N. (2019). The historical significance of "dastur ul-muluk" ("guide to the kings") by khoja samandar termizi. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(6), 2020.